

PARACHOR AND RING STRUCTURE. PART I

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The structural value for the parachor of a ring containing n -members is not independent of the nature of the members constituting the ring and hence is not the same even when n is the same. When two rings are superimposed the parachor decreases.

Sugden ("Parachor and Valency," p. 39) believes that the value calculated for six membered ring from the consideration of benzene ring holds for all rings of six, whether they may be of benzene type or not. It was suggested from our laboratories [Thesis submitted for M.Sc., 1942, 1944 by Moghe and Desai (unpublished) to Agra University] that the view needs modification. Mumford and Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 155; 1929, 2112; *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1818) were the first who objected to Sugden's procedure. Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 300, 304) holds similar view. In this part of the paper, Sugden's values for ring structures have been considered. The recent work of Pauling (*Chem. Rev.*, 1921, 6, 185; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1367, 3225; 1932, 54, 988, 3570; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 362, 606, 679) on resonance has changed our ideas of fixed structures of organic compounds which may resonate between various possible forms and hence produce net effect due to all, yet the determination of structure by parachor has its own value.

Bhatnagar and Singh (*J. chim. phys.*, 1928, 26, 21) have calculated the parachor of naphthalene ring to be equal to 9.3. Sugden suggested that the value of naphthalene ring might be best represented if it is supposed to be composed of two separate six membered rings. Assuming this value 12.2 they determined the parachor of several compounds of naphthalene. The parachor of acenaphthalene was determined by Dutoit and Friedrich (*Arch. Sci. Phys. Nat.*, 1900, 9, 105). The following table shows that the value 12.2 gives better results than the value 9.3. However, the naphthalene ring structure is not exactly twice of that of benzene as one side with double bond is common and as such it is expected that the value should be less than twice that of benzene ring or less than 12.2. The value should be calculated by the usual method, *i.e.*, by subtracting the calculated value without naphthalene ring from the observed values. This has been done in the present investigation and the results are recorded below.

TABLE I

Substance.	P (obs.).	P (calc.) with 12.2.	P (calc.) with 9.3.	P (calc.) without ring.	Difference of value of the ring
Naphthalene	312.5	313.0	310	300.8	11.7
Acenaphthalene	364.2	365.3	362.4	353.1	11.1
α -Bromonaphthalene	362.6	363.9	361.0	351.7	10.9
α -Naphthol	326.5	326.3	323.4	314.1	12.4
α -Naphthylamine	341.6	342.6	338.7	330.4	11.2
β -Naphthylamine	341.6	342.6	338.7	330.4	11.2
Mean ...					11.45 <i>i.e.</i> 11.5

The structural value 11.5 for naphthalene ring will reproduce values better than the value 12.2 and hence it is suggested as the correct value for the parachor of naphthalene ring. The value as expected is less than that of two benzene rings.

The value of the parachor of phenanthrene determined by Bhatnagar and Singh (*loc. cit.*) is 414.1, while the calculated value on the basis of three benzene rings is 418.9. Comparison of the structure of phenanthrene shows that it is less than three benzene rings as two sides are common and is also less than the sum of naphthalene and benzene ring as one side is common.

Benzene

Naphthalene

Phenanthrene

And hence its ring parachor is expected to be less than $3 \times 6 = 18$ and $11.5 + 6.1 = 17.6$. The value calculated for phenanthrene omitting the value of the ring is 400.6. This differs from the observed value 414.1 by 13.5. The ring value for phenanthrene is therefore 13.5, and is in accordance with our expectation that it should be less than 18 and also 17.6.

Paraldehyde is formed by the condensation of three molecules of acetaldehyde and its parachor is found by Schiff (*Annalen*, 1884, 223, 47), Morgan and Stone, (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1505) and Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177). This corresponds to cyclic formulae. The value calculated for cyclic formulae assuming the contribution of the ring as 6.1 is 300.1, while for open chain it is 317.2 and for (CH_2, CHO) , it is 363.6.

Here again the observed value is less by 1.4 units than the calculated value for ring structure. This is obvious because the ring is quite different from benzene ring. Not only does it contain the oxygen atoms in the ring but the double bonds are absent.

The work of Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 501) on five and six membered rings supports these views although Ray himself has failed to note the difference between pyridine ring and benzene ring.

TABLE II

Substance.	P (obs.).	P (calc.) without ring.	P ring.
Pyridine	197.4	191.6	5.8
Piperidine	230.0	224.6	5.4
Picoline	236.3	230.6	5.7

It is therefore concluded that pyridine ring has a structural value 5.7. It is further to be noted that piperidine ring which contains no double bond has a value slightly differ-

ent from the other two. Ray's work (*loc. cit.*) on five membered ring compounds, pyrrole, and succinimide gives as low a value as 3.1 in place of the accepted value 8.5 while inden, phthalic anhydride and indole, which contain a ring of six in addition, gives much lower values than 14.6 which is obtained purely on additive basis. The fact that the observed value is lower than the sum of two rings again supports the view that when two rings are superimposed the value tends to decrease.

TABLE III

Substance.	P (obs.).	P (calc.) without ring	Difference (obs.)	Difference (theor.)
Inden	284.9	272.8	12.1	14.6
Phthalic anhydride	295.1	282.8	12.3	14.6
Indole	270.2	263.4	6.8	14.6

It is obvious therefore that the parachor is not a strictly additive function depending on the number of atoms in a ring, but also depends on the nature of the atoms constituting the ring.

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